

NODIVERGENT TIPDAGI DIFFUZIYA TENGLAMASI UCHUN KOSHI MASALASINI TATQIQ QILISH

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O‘zbekiston.

$\Omega = \{(t, x) \mid t \geq t_0 = \text{const} > 0, x \in \mathbb{R}^N, N \geq 1\}$ sohada quyidagi tenglama qaraymiz:

$$Au = |x|^{-n_1} u_t - u^q \operatorname{div} \left(|x|^n u^{m-1} |\nabla u|^k \right)^{p-2} \nabla u + |x|^{-n_1} t^l u^\beta = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$u(t, x) \Big|_{t=t_0} = u_0(x) \geq 0, x \in \mathbb{R}^N. \quad (2)$$

$q < 1, k \geq 0, m, \beta \geq 1, p \geq 2, l, n, n_1$ berilgan o‘zgarmlar va $u_0(x)$ - nomanfiy, notrivial boshlang‘ich shart. (1) tenglama qator fizik - kimyoviy jarayonlarni ifodalaydi: bir jinsli bo‘lmagan muhitlarda issiqlik tarqalish jarayonini, bir jinsli bo‘lmagan muhitlardagi suyuqlik va gazning filtratsiyasi jarayonini, bir jinsli bo‘lmagan muhitlarda reaksiya diffuziya va boshqa chiziqli bo‘lmagan jarayonlarni ifodalaydi.

(1) tenglama xususiy hollarda bir qancha olimlar va tadqiqotchilar tomonidan o‘rganilgan. Xususan, (1) tenglamani zichlik hadisiz manba holida, (1)-(2) masala yechimining sifat xossalari [4] muallif tomonidan tatqiq qilingan. [9] maqolada muallif bir jinsli, $n = n_1 = 0$ va harakatlanuvchi muhitlarda (1)-(2) masala uchun global yechimlarning mavjudlik sharti yoki kritik Fujita ko‘rsatkichini aniqlagan. (1) tenglamani divergent va sistema ko‘rinishida $q = 0, l = 0, n_1 = 0$ holida Matyakubov [8], Raxmonov va Alimov [10] o‘z ilmiy ishlarida o‘rgangan va Koshi yoki Neyman masalalari uchun global yechimlarning mavjudlik va mavjud bo‘lmashlik shartlarini aniqlashgan. Martynenko va Tedeev [6] quyidagi tenglamalar uchun Koshi masalasini tatqiq etishgan:

$$\rho(x)u_t = \operatorname{div}(u^{m-1} |\nabla u|^{\lambda-1} \nabla u) + u^p, x \in \mathbb{R}^N, t > 0, \quad (3)$$

va

$$\rho(x)u_t = \operatorname{div}(u^{m-1} |\nabla u|^{\lambda-1} \nabla u) + \rho(x)u^p, x \in \mathbb{R}^N, t > 0. \quad (4)$$

Bu yerda $\lambda > 0, m + \lambda - 2 > 0, p > m + \lambda - 1, \rho(x) = |x|^{-n}$ yoki $\rho(x) = (1 + |x|)^{-n}$.

Martynenko va Tedeev (3)-(4) tenglamada koeffitsientlar ma'lum bir shartlarni qanoatlantirganda (3)-(4) tenglamalar uchun Koshi masalasining yechimi chekli vaqtda cheksizlikka intilishini (blow-up) ko'rsatib o'tishgan [7].

Andreuchchi D. va Tedeev A.F. [1] quyidagi tenglama uchun Koshi masalasini yechim uchun quyi-yuqori chegaralar baholarini olishgan va yechimlarni fazoviy lokallasuvi ko'rsatishgan

$$u_t = \operatorname{div}\left(u^{m-1} |Du|^{\lambda-1} Du\right) + f(x)u^p,$$

bunda f - Lebeg o'lchovi ma'nosida chegaralanmagan yoki $x \rightarrow 0$ da buziluvchan bo'lishi ham mumkin.

(1) tenglamaning divergent va nodivergent ko'rinishlarida $q = n_1 = n = l = 0, p = 2$ va $q = n_1 = l = 0$ hollarida Koshi masalasini J.Vazquez G'ovak muhitlar tenglamalari [11] kitobida Koshi masalasi yoki Dirak delta funksiyasi bilan berilgan Koshi masalasi yechimlarining mavjudlik sharti, mavjud bo'lmashlik sharti, L^p va $W^{k,p}$ fazolarda yechimlarning invariantligini o'rgangan.

Ma'lumki, (1) tenglama buziluvchan [3]. Shu sababli, $u = 0, \nabla u = 0$ bo'lgan sohalarda (1)-(2) masala klassik ma'noda yechimga ega bo'lmaydi. Shuning uchun bu hollarda $0, u(t, x), \operatorname{div}\left(|x|^n u^{m-1} |\nabla u^k|^{p-2} \nabla u\right) \in C(\Omega)$ sinfga tegishli, (1) tenglamani integral taqsimot ma'nosida qanoatlantiruvchi [2] umumlashgan yechimlarni qaraymiz.

(1) tenglamada $v = u^{1-q}$ belgilash kiritamiz va Au operator quyidagicha ko'rinishga keladi:

$$Au = |x|^{-n_1} v_t - \operatorname{div}\left(|x|^n v^{m_2-1} |\nabla v^{k_2}|^{p-2} \nabla v\right) + (1-q)|x|^{-n_1} t^l v^{\beta_2} = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$v|_{t=t_0} = v_0(x) = (u_0(x))^{1-q}. \quad (6)$$

Bu yerda: $m_2 = \frac{m-q}{1-q}, k_2 = \frac{k}{1-q}, \beta_2 = \frac{\beta-q}{1-q}$.

Ω sohaga l_2 normani kiritamiz va $r = |x|_{l_2}$ bo'lsin. U holda, (6) tenglamani quyidagicha yozib olamiz:

$$Au = r^{-n_1} v_t - r^{1-N} \left(r^{n+N-1} v^{m_2-1} \left| \left(v^{k_2} \right)_r \right|^{p-2} v_r \right) + (1-q) r^{-n_1} t^l v^{\beta_2} = 0, \quad (7)$$

(7) tenglamaning yechimini quyidagicha ko‘rinishda qidiramiz:

$$v(t, r) = t^{-\alpha} f(\xi), \xi = rt^{-\mu}. \quad (8)$$

Bu yerda

$$\alpha = \frac{(n_1 + 1)(p - n - n_1)}{d}, \mu = \frac{\beta_2 - 1 - (n_1 + 1)(m_2 + k_2(p - 2) - 1)}{d},$$

$$d = (\beta_2 - 1)(p - n - n_1) \neq 0.$$

(8) belgilashni (7) tenglikka kiritamiz va (7) tenglama quyidagi ko‘rinishga kelishini ko‘rish qiyin emas

$$\xi^{1-N} \frac{d}{d\xi} \left(\xi^{N-1+n} f^{m_2-1} \left| \frac{df^{k_2}}{d\xi} \right|^{p-2} \frac{df}{d\xi} \right) + \mu \xi^{1-n_1} \frac{df}{d\xi} + \alpha \xi^{-n_1} f - (1-q) \xi^{-n_1} f^{\beta_2} = 0. \quad (9)$$

Boshlang‘ich shartga muvofiq, (9) tenglamaning notrivial, nomanfiy va quyidagi shartlarini qanoatlantiruvchi yechimlarini qidiramiz:

$$f'(0) = f(b) = 0, 0 < b < +\infty. \quad (10)$$

Quyidagicha belgilash kiritamiz:

$$z(x, t) = t^{-\alpha} \bar{f}(\xi), \bar{f}(\xi) = A \left(\xi_0^{\gamma_1} - \xi^{\gamma_1} \right)_+^{\gamma_2} \quad (11)$$

Bu yerda:

$$\gamma_1 = \frac{p}{p-1}, \gamma_2 = \frac{p-1}{m_2 + k_2(p-2) - 1}, A = \left(\frac{p-1}{p\gamma_2} \left(\frac{1}{pk_2^{p-2}} \right)^{\frac{1}{p-1}} \right)^{\gamma_2}, (b)_+ = \max(b, 0), \xi_0 = \text{const} \geq 0.$$

Teorema. $v(t, x)$ (3)-(4) masalaning umumlashgan yechimi bo‘lsin va quyidagi tengsizliklar

$$\gamma_2 > 0, p > n + n_1, \beta_2 > \beta_{2c} = 1 + (1+l) \left(m_2 + k_2(p-2) - 1 + \frac{p-n-n_1}{N-n_1} \right) \quad \text{va}$$

$v(x, t_0) \leq z(x, t_0), x \in R^N$, o‘rinli bo‘lsin. U holda, Ω sohada (3)-(4) masalaning yechimi uchun quyidagi baho o‘rinli:

$$v(t, x), z(t, x).$$

Isbot. Teoremani isbotlash uchun taqqoslash prinsipini qo‘llaymiz [2] va $z(t, x)$ funksiyani taqqoslovchi funksiya sifatida tanlaymiz. (11) belgilashni (3) tenglikka kiritamiz va quyidagi tenglikka ega bo‘lamiz:

$$\xi^{1-N} \frac{d}{d\xi} \left(\xi^{N-1+n} \bar{f}^{m_2-1} \left| \frac{d\bar{f}^{k_2}}{d\xi} \right|^{p-2} \frac{d\bar{f}}{d\xi} \right) + \mu \xi^{1-n_1} \frac{d\bar{f}}{d\xi} + \alpha \xi^{-n_1} \bar{f} - (1-q) \xi^{-n_1} \bar{f}^{\beta_2} \leq 0. \quad (12)$$

$$\bar{f}(\xi) \text{ funksiyani } \frac{d}{d\xi} \left(\xi^{N-1+n} \bar{f}^{m_2-1} \left| \frac{d\bar{f}^{k_2}}{d\xi} \right|^{p-2} \frac{d\bar{f}}{d\xi} \right) + \mu \frac{d}{d\xi} (\xi^{N-n_1} \bar{f}) = 0 \text{ tenglamani yechimi}$$

ekanligi sababli, (12) tengsizlikni quyidagicha yozib olamiz:

$$-\xi^{N-1-n_1} \bar{f} \left((1-q) \bar{f}^{\beta_2-1} + \mu(N-n_1) - \alpha \right) \leq 0. \quad (13)$$

$\xi, \bar{f} \geq 0$ va $\gamma_2 > 0, p > n + n_1, \beta_2 > \beta_{2c}$ yoki $\mu(N-n_1) \leq \alpha$ ekanligidan (13) tengsizlik har doim bajariladi. U holda, $z(t_0, x) \geq v_0(x), x \in \square^N$, bo'lsa, Ω sohada $v(t, x) \leq z(t, x)$ tengsizlik o'rinli. Teorema isbotlandi.

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